

Original Research

Impact of Understanding Tax Regulations, Fiscus Service Quality, and Tax Sanctions on Taxpayer Compliance Moderated by Risk Preference

Hali Siti Halimah¹
Department of Accounting, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas
Swadaya Gunung Jati, 45132 Cirebon, Indonesia

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to examine the understanding of tax regulations, the quality of fiscal services, and tax sanctions on individual taxpayer compliance, as well as risk preferences that act as moderating variables, will be examined in this study. Primary data was used in this study through a survey using a questionnaire. Primary data consists of respondents' responses from external sources through filling out questionnaires. This study aims to comprehend tax regulation, the quality of service provided by tax authorities, tax penalties, and risk preferences at the Ciayumajakuning Tax Office. The population for this study consists of 1,054,320. The sample size calculation method used in this study is the total number of samples by using the sample size calculator function available on the www.raosoft.com website, yielding a total of 271 individuals. The partial least square (PLS) data analysis technique uses the software smartPLS version 4 to apply the Structural Equation Model (SEM) based on component or variation data. Although risk preferences have no effect on taxpayer compliance, understanding tax regulations, the quality of tax authorities' services and tax sanctions affect tax compliance.

Keywords: Quality of fiscal services, risk preferences taxpayer compliance, tax sanctions, understanding of tax regulations.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: agung789@gmail.com

Introduction

Over time, government programmes will be implemented in more diverse ways over time, and will continue to grow each year. National development is an activity undertaken by the government with the goal of enhancing people's welfare in a fair and equitable manner in accordance with the implementation of the 1945 Constitution, as part of the fulfillment of the mission of the 1945 Constitution (Wahyuningsih, 2019). In a worldwide setting, taxes are generally seen as one of the primary sources of a nation's overall domestic revenue (Lutfi et al., 2023).

According to Article 1 paragraph 1 of KUP Law No. 28 of 2007, tax is an obligatory payment made to the government by persons or companies that is compelled under the law and that serves the state's goals—namely, the prosperity of the populace—instead of receiving a direct benefit. According to the Ministry of Finance, the State Budget's (APBN) revenue streams demonstrate the significant role that taxes play in providing funds for development.

Table 1. State Revenue 2017-2023

Year	Taxation (%)	PNBP (%)	Grant (%)
2017	91,5	119,6	3,1
2018	93,9	148,6	1,2
2019	86,6	107,8	0,4
2020	91,5	116,9	1,3
APBNP 2021	107,2	153,8	0,9
2022	103,6	109,5	0,8
APBN 2023	86,3	112,0	0,4

Source: www.kemenkeu.go.id/APBN 2017-2023

If we look at the data in Table 1 regarding State Revenue from 2017 to 2023, there are significant fluctuations. Tax revenue dropped dramatically to only 86.3% of total state revenue in the 2023 State Budget, while in the 2021 state budget, it reached 107.2% of total state revenue. This indicates a low level of taxpayer compliance. They feel that they do not directly benefit from tax payments. Tax revenue will decrease for the government if citizens are not obedient in paying taxes (Wahyuningsih, 2019).

In Indonesia, the tax collection has used a self-assessment tax system (Sindik et al., 2022). As autonomous subjects of the tax system, taxpayers are dependent on the self-assessment system to determine, pay, and report the amount of tax owed in compliance with tax laws and regulations, as stated by Jihin et al., (2021). The act of following the guidelines provided by tax legislation in order to meet the obligation to pay taxes is known as tax compliance. Conversely, non-compliance denotes either failing to pay any tax at all or paying less than what is required (Palys & Palys, 2022).

One of the numerous factors influencing taxpayers' ability to fulfil their tax payment obligations is their understanding of tax legislation. Understanding the fundamentals of tax policy is crucial because it affects people's willingness to voluntarily comply with the

tax system (Lutfi et al., 2023), (Faisal & Yulianto, 2019). This is particularly true in properly assessing one's tax obligations. A taxpayer needs to know the procedures for paying taxes, reporting tax returns, and other related matters. Taxpayers' ignorance is the cause of their non-compliance with tax regulations. Thus, this makes taxpayers less motivated to fulfil their tax obligations (Nasiroh & Afiqoh, 2022). The purpose of this study is to investigate issues related to tax law comprehension, the calibre of services rendered by tax authorities, and the effect of taxes on taxpayer compliance. It centres on each taxpayer's degree of compliance. Risk aversion is considered in the study's conclusions as a moderating factor that affects the level of taxpayer compliance.

To increase taxpayer compliance with their responsibilities, tax regulations should incorporate the principles of fairness, transparency, and simplicity (Lailiyah et al., 2024). Furthermore, taxpayers want to get the most assistance available. Perceptions of the quality of tax services may influence taxpayer compliance, especially if tax authorities increase service expectations. However, a decline in service quality can negatively impact taxpayer compliance and public confidence in the government (Lutfi et al., 2023). The accuracy and promptness with which the Tax Return (SPT) is submitted to the Tax Service Office (KPP) reveal the extent of taxpayer compliance. Lack of knowledge about the processes involved in submitting annual tax returns, a lack of socialization from the tax office, and the physical distance separating taxpayers and the tax office are some of the barriers that could prevent taxpayers from submitting their returns on time or cause delays (Suhartanto & Morasa, 2015).

According to applicable tax legislation, taxpayers must file an Annual Tax Return (SPT) each period and year to indicate the amount of taxes that must be paid and how those taxes were calculated. SPT submission must be done before the tax reporting deadline, while tax payments must be completed before the payment deadline. Administrative penalties, such as fines, interest, or an increase in the amount of tax due, will be imposed for missing the reporting or payment date (Hasibuan et al., 2020). Sanctions are thought to be one of the most effective ways to put an end to undesirable behaviour (Lutfi et al., 2023).

Compared to 2022, when annual tax return reporting by individual taxpayers reached 6.1 per cent, this year's growth is slower. Despite lower growth in individuals compared to the previous year, the overall number of taxpayers continues to grow, the Ministry of Finance's Director General of Taxes, Suryo Utomo, said in a media session on Thursday (11/5/2023).

Suryo reports that the deadlines for filing individual taxpayer annual tax returns and corporate taxpayer annual tax returns are set for 31 March 2023 and 30 April 2023, respectively. The administration has "extended" the deadline for reporting till the end of the year. Nevertheless, taxpayers who file after the deadline will be fined IDR 1 million for corporations and IDR 100,000 for individual taxpayers. Out of the 20 million taxpayers enrolled in the government database, the administration expects 19.44 million of them to file annual tax returns by the end of this year. "We will continue to monitor the progress until the end of this year," he said. Overall, annual tax return reporting using electronic channels, both e-filing and e-form, has also increased this year. As many as 96 per cent of taxpayers who reported their tax returns as of 10 May 2023 have used

electronic channels. The use of electronic channels to report SPT is expected to facilitate the public in the reporting process and increase the level of compliance.

Table 2. Number of Individual Taxpayers at KPP Ciayumajakuning
 Year 2019-2023

KPP Pratama Cirebon Satu						
No	Types of Individual Taxpayers	Total				
		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1.	Active WPOP	28.923	30.250	31.518	33.428	35.079

KPP Pratama Cirebon Dua						
No	Types of Individual Taxpayers	Total				
		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1.	Active WPOP	56.519	61.050	63.949	66.601	75.256

KPP Pratama Indramayu						
No	Types of Individual Taxpayers	Total				
		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1.	Active WPOP	44.624	45.516	46.426	47.354	48.328

KPP Pratama Majalengka and KPP Pratama Kuningan						
No	Types of Individual Taxpayers	Total				
		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1.	Active WPOP	34.536	213.197	28.708	31.720	31.339

Source: Processed from KPP Pratama Ciayumajakuning

KPP Ciayumajakuning was selected as the research site by the researchers in this study in order to obtain information regarding the compliance of individual taxpayers. KPP Ciayumajakuning was chosen because there was an increase in individual taxpayer registration at KPP Pratama Ciayumajakuning between 2019 and 2023. Ciayumajakuning is a combination of Cirebon, Indramayu, Majalengka, and Kuningan. Because Kuningan and Majalengka regencies are contiguous and comprise similar areas, the number of active WPOP (taxpayers) in both regencies is combined. Kuningan Regency is adjacent to Majalengka Regency in the west, and some areas of Kuningan Regency are located west of Majalengka Regency. These two districts also consist of many related villages and sub-districts, so the number of active WPOPs in the district will be one of the factors that affect the regional and economic balance in the area. The purpose of this study is to determine whether the personal risk preferences of taxpayers affect their compliance, their level of risk awareness, the penalties they face, and their knowledge of tax rules.

Under the direction of the Directorate General of Taxes, KPP Pratama Ciayumajakuning operates as a branch of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia. KPP Pratama Ciayumajakuning's goal is to collect state taxes through the implementation of tax laws that uphold the state's fiscal stability through effective and

efficient tax management. KPP Pratama Ciayumajakuning's primary duties include auditing, supervising, advising, counselling, and collecting sales, value-added, and income taxes on upscale items. KPP's tasks include data collection and processing, distribution of tax information, evaluation of tax potential, research, administration of periodic and annual tax returns, filing on behalf of taxpayers, scrutiny, collection, imposition or execution of fines, and execution of tax operations. Therefore, the role of tax service offices has important significance in the implementation of tax operations at the national level.

This study highlights the phenomenon of increasing number of taxpayers, but unfortunately the state revenue from taxation was decreased in 2023. Additionally, previous research in the context of taxpayer compliance only focused in tax regulations, and service quality. Research that considering risk preference factor is still lacking, therefore this study explores the moderating role of risk preference in determining taxpayer compliance. Based on this problem, these factors can encourage researchers to conduct similar research. However, there will be differences between the planned research and previous research in terms of population and sample, research time, and research place, as well as research methods. By considering the existing research factors, the research questions of this study are (1) What is the influence of Understanding Tax Regulations, Fiscal Service Quality, and Tax Sanctions on Individual Taxpayer Compliance? (2) What is the moderating role of Risk Preference in predicting taxpayer compliance.

Literature Review

Grounded Theory

Compliance theory

Compliance theory explains a situation in which an individual complies with an order. When taxpayers try to understand and fulfil their responsibilities by established guidelines and based on applicable laws and regulations, this is referred to as taxpayer compliance. One could argue that taxpayer compliance and compliance theory are closely related because taxpayer compliance describes the circumstances in which taxpayers can fulfil their duties and exercise their right to pay taxes. In contrast, compliance theory explains the circumstances in which an individual complies with rules or regulations. Other theories regarding taxpayer compliance include social learning, prospect theory, and attribution theory. As defined by the Minister of Finance Regulation No. 192/PMK.03/2007 on Taxpayers with certain criteria in the context of preliminary refund of tax overpayment, Compliant Taxpayers refer to taxpayers who fulfil the following conditions:

- a. Submitting notification letter on time.
- b. Calculate and pay taxes correctly and on time.
- c. There are no tax arrears for all types of taxes except for tax arrears for which the taxpayer has received permission to install or postpone tax payments.

- d. Financial statements audited by a public accountant or government financial supervision agency with an unqualified opinion for three consecutive years.
- e. I have never been convicted of a criminal offence in the field of taxation based on a court decision that has permanent legal force within the last five years.

Individual Taxpayers

Everyone who has an income above the non-taxable income is considered an individual taxpayer. Unless otherwise mandated by law, all individuals in Indonesia must register and obtain a Taxpayer Identification Number (NPWP).

Taxpayer Compliance

When taxpayers try to understand and fulfil their responsibilities by established guidelines and based on applicable laws and regulations, this is referred to as taxpayer compliance. (Illahi & Marlina, 2018) State that there are five indicators of taxpayer compliance variables, including:

1. Reporting tax returns on time, all taxpayers are required to submit tax returns on time to avoid penalties for delays.
2. Calculate and pay taxes correctly and on time, to ensure that there is no overpayment or underpayment, each taxpayer must calculate the tax with the correct amount and on time.
3. Have no tax arrears, every taxpayer should pay all taxes due and have no outstanding tax debts to fulfill their tax obligations and avoid sanctions or fines from the tax authorities.
4. Not violating the rules or being sentenced to criminal penalties in the field of taxation, each taxpayer has complied with applicable tax provisions and is not involved in violations of the law that could result in criminal sanctions.
5. Make records correctly, to prevent under- or overpayments, each taxpayer is required to record their income correctly.

Understanding of Tax Regulations

In order to accomplish tax-related chores, such as filing tax returns and paying payments, taxpayers must use their understanding of tax laws, rules, and procedures. Taxpayer compliance will increase if people understand and are aware of taxes. (As'ari & Erawati, 2018) According to his research, several indicators indicate that taxpayers are aware of tax regulations, such as:

1. With knowledge of the general provisions and procedures of taxation, those who know taxes will be better able to fulfill their tax obligations and avoid adverse legal problems in the future.
2. With knowledge of taxation functions, each taxpayer can fulfill their tax obligations correctly and understand the importance of paying taxes.
3. Compliance in calculating and paying taxes correctly, Each taxpayer is required to understand their tax responsibilities and complete them by applicable regulations to ensure the calculation and payment of taxes correctly.

Quality of Fiskus Service

The ability to satisfy taxpayers' needs while upholding accountability and providing services that must be delivered on a regular or recurring basis defines the standard of fiscal services. In addition to determining the amount of tax owed, tax authorities now have other duties, such as monitoring, servicing, consulting, and enforcing tax penalties. To best assist taxpayers in this regard, it is essential to comprehend the rights and obligations of tax officers.

(As'ari & Erawati, 2018) State that five indicators can be used to measure fiscal service quality variables. These are the following indicators.:

1. Reliability.
2. Responsiveness.
3. Assurances.
4. Empathy.
5. Tangibles.

Tax Sanctions

To put it another way, the purpose of tax penalties is to dissuade taxpayers from breaking the law. The imposition of tax penalties ensures compliance with regulations. Tax penalties are imposed for violations of tax laws and regulations. When a violation occurs, taxpayers are sanctioned by tax policy or legal indications. (As'ari, 2018) States that three indicators form the instrument used to measure this variable.

1. Tax sanctions imposed for violators of tax rules are quite severe.
2. The use of severe tax sanctions is one of the suggestions to educate taxpayers.
3. Tax sanctions must be imposed on violators without tolerance.

Risk Preference

Risk-taking propensity is a feature of several theories of decision-making. This prospect theory offers a theoretical foundation for moderating risk preferences with regard to taxpayer compliance and comprehension of tax legislation, the calibre of services rendered by tax authorities, and tax sanctions. (Wahyuningsih, 2019) According to this idea, taxpayer compliance will be influenced by a high level of risk for taxpayers. (C. Safitri, 2018) states that five indicators can be used to measure the risk preference quality variable. These indicators are as follows:

1. Financial Risk

A person's financial condition is linked to financial risk. A person with investments cannot eliminate all risks, including the possibility of losing money and not receiving dividends. Also, financial risks cannot be avoided by entrepreneurs. The important thing to remember is that everyone who files for bankruptcy is exposing themselves to risk. This will have an impact on how one files taxes as a taxpayer.

2. Health Risks

The ability to perform various tasks is undoubtedly affected by one's health. Being a taxpayer is one of them. The actions of chronic disease patients as taxpayers will undoubtedly be affected. Tax-related activities will also be affected by individuals with mental illness or abnormalities from birth. Of course, tax-related activities do not always go as planned.

3. Social Risk.

Social risk relates to the condition of the surrounding community. This study highlights social risk in the interaction between taxpayers and tax authorities. These interactions will affect tax compliance. Subsequently, societal hazards associated with government tax policy changes will affect taxpayer compliance regarding tax payments.

4. Occupational Risk.

A person's life is greatly impacted by their work, and taxpayers are no exception. Taxpayer compliance may vary depending on the type and status of one's job. Individuals with irregular employment usually comply less with tax regulations. People who lose their jobs often do not realize that they still have a tax liability bill.

5. Safety Risks

In this study, job risk is associated with safety risk. There is a threat to the safety of employees in the workplace. Because they fail to ensure safety at work, someone has a problem or accident. This has implications for taxpayer compliance.

Learning and comprehending the relevant tax rules and regulations is the process of understanding tax regulations. A taxpayer is expected to be able to understand how to manage taxes, payments, reporting, and other related tasks. All aspects of taxation that taxpayers can understand are included in taxpayer understanding (Ridhotin, 2022). The more knowledgeable and comprehending a taxpayer is about tax regulations, the more likely they are to comply with their rights and obligations.

The quality of service provided to taxpayers by tax authorities has a direct effect on taxpayer compliance. Tax officers are required to provide responsible, moral, and expert services to taxpayers. The primary responsibilities of the KPP Pratama are to assist taxpayers with tax-related law enforcement, counselling, and supervision (Ramadhanty & Zulaikha, 2020). Therefore, the level of taxpayer compliance may be influenced by the quality of services offered by tax authorities. Taxpayer compliance has a direct bearing on service quality.

Regulations regarding tax penalties are found in the tax code's general requirements and procedures. Sanctions must be applied to educate tax violators. The imposition of tax sanctions has the fundamental objective of preventing violations and ensuring taxpayer compliance with their obligations (Nasiroh & Afiqoh, 2022). Taxpayers are encouraged to complete their obligations more responsibly by the imposition of sanctions on tax cheaters.

When it comes to meeting their tax payment obligations, taxpayers are faced with many risks. Taxpayers' perspectives on the hazards they face can influence the decisions they make (Utari & Setiawan, 2019). There are two main components in the notion of risk preference: facing risks and avoiding risks. Taxpayer shows a high level of risk preference when they can cope with the hazards that may occur and are ready to do so. When a taxpayer is prepared to bear the risks involved in filing taxes or other hazards, they are said to have a high-risk preference.

Taxpayer understanding is the ability to understand the applicable tax collection process by applicable rules and regulations. On the other hand, risk preference relates to the type of risk that can affect taxpayers' perceptions of their tax compliance. The taxpayer's decision to pay taxes or not will depend on how well-informed they are about the risks involved. When the risks associated with taxpayers are moderated, there is a tendency for taxpayers' compliance with their tax obligations to increase. This risk consists of not knowing what will happen in the future, which can impact one or more goals in a positive way (gain) or in a bad way (loss) ((Elsani & Tanno, 2023).

A collection of measures implemented to assist in meeting the demands of taxpayers is referred to as "taxpayer services". By offering effective fiscal services, taxpayer compliance can be raised. The risks that taxpayers confront, both large and minor, might affect how compliant they are with their tax obligations (R. Wulandari, 2020a). A person's tendency to take risks has an impact on the choices they make in terms of tax reporting, especially in situations where there is danger. Taxpayers who face no risk will usually be highly compliant with the law. However, taxpayers are less likely to abide by tax regulations and may even choose to forego paying taxes when they face large risks (Mei & Firmansyah, 2022).

The idea that taxpayers will inevitably comply with or obey tax regulations is reflected in tax sanctions (Soda et al., 2021). The amount of loss that taxpayers will bear increases along with the severity of the penalty. Tax penalties typically cause taxpayers to suffer a sizable enough loss that they will abide by their tax responsibilities. This suggests that the imposition of tax penalties increases taxpayer compliance. Considering risk preferences can help enforce harsh tax penalties that are perceived as detrimental to taxpayers. Therefore, a taxpayer is more likely to choose to pay their taxes if they have a high level of risk preference.

Previous Research Results

Research was done by (Dinata et al., 2023) on how individual taxpayer compliance is affected by the self-assessment system, tax knowledge and comprehension, and Machiavellian. The results demonstrate that, when considering tax knowledge and comprehension, individual taxpayer compliance has a significant positive impact. The study's findings are consistent with earlier research (Michael et al., 2013), (As'ari & Erawati, 2018), (Wahyuningsih, 2019), and (Purba, 2016) which found a good relationship between taxpayer compliance and taxpayer compliance. However, this contradicts the research of (Nasiroh & Afiqoh, 2022) and (R. N. Safitri & Afiqoh, 2022) which demonstrate that tax knowledge has little bearing on an individual taxpayer's compliance.

The effect of taxpayer knowledge and fiscal services on individual taxpayer compliance with the tax administration system was investigated (Yuliadi, 2018). The information demonstrates that fiscal services have a favourable impact on taxpayer compliance. The outcomes of this study corroborate earlier research (Yuliadi, 2017) and (Hasanah et al., 2020), indicating that fiscal services affect taxpayer compliance. This, however, runs counter to studies by (Siahaan & Halimatusyadiah, 2018) and (Wijayanto, 2018), which demonstrate that fiscal services have little influence on the compliance of individual taxpayers.

Using the function of the account representative as a moderating variable, research by (D. S. Wulandari, 2019) investigates the effects of tax sanctions, service quality, and the usefulness of Npwp on the compliance of individual taxpayers enrolled at Kpp Pratama Cibirung. The study's conclusion demonstrates that tax penalties increase taxpayer compliance. The investigation's findings are consistent with earlier research projects carried out by (Elva Nuraina, 2017), (Nasiroh & Afiqoh, 2022), (Muliari & Setiawan, 2011), (Karnedi & Hidayatulloh, 2019), (Siahaan & Halimatusyadiah, 2018), (As'ari & Erawati, 2018), (Ngadiman & Huslin, 2015), (Hasanah et al., 2020), (D. S. Wulandari, 2019), (Wahyuningsih, 2019) and (Lutfi et al., 2023). On the other hand, research by (Michael et al., 2013) shows that tax penalties have little effect on taxpayer compliance.

Research indicates that taxpayer compliance is positively impacted by risk preference (Aziz et al., 2018). However, studies (Wahyuningsih, 2019) demonstrate that taxpayer compliance is unaffected by risk preference.

Studies conducted by (Aziz et al., 2018) and (R. Wulandari, 2020b) demonstrates that risk preferences can modify the link between taxpayer compliance and understanding of tax legislation. Research indicates otherwise (Wahyuningsih, 2019). It demonstrate that risk preferences cannot control the link between taxpayer compliance and tax law knowledge.

An empirical study (Aziz et al., 2018) at KPP Pratama Singosari examined the moderating role of risk preference in the relationship between taxpayer compliance and understanding of tax legislation. The results showed that the relationship between taxpayer compliance and the quality of fiscal services may be influenced by risk preferences. This claim is contradicted by research (Wahyuningsih, 2019), which shows that risk preferences are unable to mediate the relationship between taxpayer compliance and the quality of fiscal services.

Studies have indicated that the relationship between taxpayer compliance and the efficacy of tax punishments can be influenced by risk preference (Aziz et al., 2018) and (R. Wulandari, 2020b). However, this is contradicted by another study (Wahyuningsih, 2019). This demonstrates that risk preferences do not regulate the link between tax penalties and tax compliance.

Framework and Hypothesis

Framework of Thought

Using risk preference as a moderating variable, researchers have put forth a wide range of choices, including the effect of tax sanctions on taxpayer compliance, the caliber of services provided by tax authorities, and the understanding of tax laws. The goal of this research is to ascertain how taxpayer compliance is impacted by knowledge of tax laws, the caliber of services provided by tax authorities, and tax penalties. Moreover, the study aims to investigate the moderating impact of risk preferences on the association between these variables and specific taxpayer compliance.

Analysis of the Impact of Understanding Tax Regulations, Fiscal Service Quality, and Tax Sanctions on Individual Taxpayer Compliance with Risk Preference as a Moderating Variable

Figure 1. Framework of Thought

Hypothesis Development

Comprehending Tax Regulations' Impact on Taxpayer Compliance

Comprehending tax regulations entails that taxpayers comprehend the laws and regulations that are applicable within the tax system. The degree of taxpayer compliance increases with the level of taxpayer awareness and comprehension of tax laws. According to research by (Dinata et al., 2023), individual taxpayer compliance is significantly positively impacted by knowledge and comprehension of taxes.

H₁: Comprehending tax regulations positively impacts the compliance of taxpayers..

Fiskus Service Quality's Impact on Taxpayer Compliance

The degree of service rendered by the tax authorities is directly correlated with the degree of taxpayer compliance with regard to tax payments. Therefore, the quality of tax services provided by tax officials will have a direct impact on the degree of taxpayer compliance. As the quality of services offered improves, so does the amount of taxpayer

compliance. (Yuliadi, 2018) demonstrates how fiscal services improve taxpayer compliance.

H₂: Fiskus Service Quality influences taxpayer compliance in a favorable way.

Tax Sanctions' Impact on Taxpayer Compliance

Tax sanctions are one of the weapons used by the government to emphasize public responsibility for its obligations. The imposition of tax sanctions is mainly done to encourage taxpayer compliance in paying taxes. Research conducted (D. S. Wulandari, 2019), (Nasiroh & Afiqoh, 2022), (Hasanah et al., 2020), and (Wahyuningsih, 2019) showed that tax sanctions have a positive and significant effect on taxpayer compliance.

H₃: Taxpayer compliance benefits from tax sanctions.

Risk Preference's Impact on Taxpayer Compliance

A person's risk preferences are one of the theories connected to decision-making, along with the prospect of tax compliance and rationality theory. (Aziz et al., 2018) demonstrates that risk preferences positively impact taxpayer compliance.

H₄: Taxpayer compliance is positively impacted by risk preference.

The Moderating Variable of Taxpayer Compliance with Risk Preference: The Impact of Comprehending Tax Regulations

Taxpayers can comprehend tax laws, rules, and procedures by having a solid understanding of tax regulations. The self-assessment approach is employed in Indonesia to collect taxes. If taxpayers understand tax regulations well, they tend to be more compliant with these regulations. The type of risk that will affect taxpayers' perception of their level of tax compliance is known as risk preference. Taxpayers will choose how much to pay after they are aware of the risks they will incur, as risk preference entails choosing risks that they will personally bear. (Aziz et al., 2018) Moreover, (R. Wulandari, 2020b) These results demonstrate how risk preference might influence the link between taxpayer compliance and tax law knowledge.

H₅: The association between taxpayer compliance and knowing tax regulations is moderated by risk preference.

The Moderating Variable of Fiskus Service Quality's Effect on Taxpayer Compliance with Risk Preference

Serving others is a procedure that involves carrying out tasks performed directly by others to meet their needs. Meanwhile, tax authorities, also known as tax officers, are those who offer tax-related services to taxpayers. Taxpayer compliance increases when tax authorities provide good service. Qualified tax officers provide accurate information regarding the procedures for calculating, depositing, and reporting taxes to taxpayers. In

addition, the attitude of tax authorities who interact well, are friendly, and the patient is expected to increase taxpayer compliance (Nugrahani & Suryaningsum, 2023). (Aziz et al., 2018) demonstrate how the risk preference variable can moderate the link between taxpayer compliance and the quality of fiskus services.

H₆: The relationship between taxpayer compliance and the caliber of services provided by tax authorities is tempered by risk preference.

The Impact of Tax Sanctions as a Moderating Variable on Taxpayer Compliance with Risk Preference

One technique to guarantee that the tax law's (or tax standards') requirements will be followed is through tax sanctions. Stated differently, the goal of tax penalties is to deter taxpayers from violating the law. The KUP Law divides tax sanctions into two categories: administrative sanctions and criminal punishments. Sanctions that are harsher or more extensive will hurt taxpayers more. Tax sanctions usually result in significant losses for taxpayers, therefore they will comply with their tax obligations. This suggests that tax penalties boost taxpayer compliance with regard to filing their taxes. To boost taxpayer compliance when risk appetite is present. On the other hand, a taxpayer is more likely to be in disobedience when there is less risk in their life. Risk preference can act as a moderator in the relationship between taxpayer compliance and the quality of tax sanctions (R. Wulandari, 2020a).

H₇: The relationship between taxpayer compliance and tax punishments is moderated by risk preference.

Methodology

Research type and approach

This study collects primary data using a questionnaire-based survey, using a quantitative research design and technique. Primary data comes from respondents who fill out questionnaires from external sources. The primary subjects of this study include risk preferences at KPP Pratama Ciayumajakuning, tax sanctions, tax law comprehension, and the calibre of services rendered by tax authorities.

Operational Variables

The operational variables of the research model is presented in Table3.

Table 3. Variable Definitions and Operations

Variables	Definition	Indicator	Measurement
Taxpayer Compliance (Y)	Taxpayer compliance, which in this study serves as the dependent variable, can be defined as a state where taxpayers strive to understand and comply with their responsibilities by the guidelines provided in the applicable laws and regulations. (Wahyuningsih, 2019)	Reporting tax returns on time. Calculate and pay taxes correctly and on time. Do not have tax arrears. Not violating the rules or being sentenced to criminal punishment in the field of taxation. Make records correctly. (Illahi & Marlina, 2018)	Likert Scale
Understanding of Tax Regulations (X1)	In this study, knowledge of tax law is an independent variable. Knowing and comprehending tax laws, rules, and procedures, as well as applying them to tax-related acts, is the process of understanding tax law. (Wahyuningsih, 2019)	Knowledge of general provisions and tax procedures. Knowledge of taxation functions. Compliance in calculating and paying taxes correctly. (As'ari & Erawati, 2018)	Likert Scale
Fiskus Service Quality (X2)	The second independent variable in this study is Fiskus Service Quality. The term "service" describes a range of initiatives designed to address people's needs by putting them in touch with tax authorities directly. Meanwhile, tax authorities or tax officers are individuals who are responsible for services and information related to taxation to taxpayers. (Wahyuningsih, 2019)	Reliability. Responsiveness. Assurances. Empathy. Tangibles. (As'ari & Erawati, 2018)	Likert Scale
Tax Sanctions (X3)	Sanctions are the third independent variable in this	The tax sanctions imposed on	Likert Scale

Variables	Definition	Indicator	Measurement
	study. One significant element that motivates someone to fulfil their tax duties is sanction. This penalty works to control conduct that violates the rules because there is a belief that the existence of control can create a perception of control over this behaviour. In other words, if someone does not comply with their tax obligations, they will be faced with sanctions that are beyond their control. (Asfa I. & Meiranto, 2017)	violators of tax rules are quite severe. The use of heavy tax sanctions is one of the suggestions to educate taxpayers. Tax sanctions must be imposed on violators without tolerance. (As'ari, 2018)	
Risk Preference (Z)	Risk preference is a moderating variable in this study. A person's risk aversion is taken into account in several decision-making theories, including ideas about tax compliance, such as prospect theory and rationality theory. (Wahyuningsih, 2019)	Financial Risk. Health Risk. Social Risk. Occupational Risks. Safety Risk. (C. Safitri, 2018)	Likert Scale

Population and Sample

The sample size for this study, which employs the accidental sampling approach, is established using the sample size calculator on the www.raosoft.com website. In the computation, a 90% confidence level, a 50% response distribution, and a 5% margin of error are used to fill in the population size column. The 1,054,320 WPOP individual taxpayers who are registered with the Ciayumajakuning Tax Office constitute the study's population. There were 271 samples obtained.

Data Collection

This study uses a questionnaire to collect data. Respondents are given a set of written questions to fill in via Google Form and provided a value or score using a Likert scale, thus giving respondents the freedom to express their opinions in the questionnaire (Purnomo, 2024).

Data Analysis Technique

To assist researchers in obtaining latent variables for prediction, partial least square (PLS) analysis is used (Ghozali, 2014, p. 31). With the use of the smartPLS software

version 4, partial least square (PLS), a component- or variant-based structural equation model (SEM), is created. Three phases of this investigation were completed, specifically:

1. Outer Model Analysis
2. Inner Model Analysis
3. Hypothesis Testing

With the following explanation:

a. Outer Model Analysis

To determine the validity or dependability of the model, an evaluation of the measurement model, also known as the outer model, is conducted. According to (Ghozali, 2015, p. 73), composite reliability, Cronbach alpha for the indicator block, and *convergent* and *discriminant validity* of latent construct generating indicators are used to evaluate outer models with reflexive indicators.

b. Inner Model Analysis

Predicting the link between latent variables is the goal of inner model analysis, sometimes referred to as structural model analysis (Ghozali, 2015, p. 73).

c. Hypothesis Test

Testimonials are conducted after numerous evaluations of the inner and outside models have been completed. The direction of the link between endogenous and exogenous factors is explained through hypothesis testing.

Results and Discussion

Table 4 lists the characteristics of the respondents who filled out the questionnaire; most of the respondents were men, with the majority aged 21-30 years, the majority education level was undergraduate, and the majority type of work was other.

Table 4. Respondent Characteristics

Respondent Characteristics		Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender			
1.	Male	162	162%
2.	Female	109	109%
Total		271	271%
Age			
1.	< 20	13	13%
2.	21 – 30 th	96	96%
3.	31 – 50 th	75	75%
4.	41 – 50 th	66	66%
5.	> 50 th	21	21%

Respondent Characteristics		Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Total		271	271%
Last Education			
1.	SMP	6	6%
2.	SMA	65	65%
3.	D1/D2/D3	28	28%
4.	Bachelor (S1)	149	149%
5.	Master (S2)	11	11%
6.	Doctor (S3)	10	10%
7.	Miscellaneous	2	2%
Total		271	271%
Type of Work			
1.	Entrepreneurship	33	33%
2.	Private Employee	50	50%
3.	PNS	86	86%
4.	TNI/POLRI	5	5%
5.	Miscellaneous	97	97%
Total		271	271%

Analysis Outer Model

Convergent Validity

Figure 2. Model Framework After Processing (After Reduction)

As can be observed from Figure 2, every indication has a loading factor value greater than 0.7, indicating that each indicator is legitimate and can move on to the following test. These findings suggest that there is a strong correlation between each component and the research indicators.

Discriminant Validity

The reflecting model's *discriminant validity* can be assessed by looking at the cross-loading values. The loading value on the intended construct must be bigger than the other values, and the cross-loadings metric examines the correlation of indicators with other block structures.

Table 5. Value of cross loadings

Variable	UTR	PSQ	TS	ITC	RF
UTR1	0,763	0,529	0,509	0,565	0,478
UTR2	0,752	0,485	0,514	0,541	0,410
UTR3	0,752	0,527	0,570	0,648	0,471
UTR4	0,704	0,538	0,437	0,491	0,369
UTR5	0,767	0,483	0,580	0,560	0,431
UTR6	0,709	0,406	0,472	0,516	0,372
UTR7	0,706	0,420	0,456	0,458	0,382
UTR8	0,748	0,475	0,389	0,514	0,340
PSQ1	0,532	0,784	0,431	0,497	0,401
PSQ10	0,486	0,779	0,426	0,490	0,377
PSQ2	0,495	0,714	0,380	0,464	0,353
PSQ3	0,524	0,752	0,474	0,479	0,411
PSQ4	0,483	0,708	0,473	0,492	0,385
PSQ5	0,475	0,792	0,353	0,504	0,372
PSQ6	0,546	0,783	0,408	0,535	0,402
PSQ7	0,506	0,717	0,455	0,527	0,398
PSQ8	0,490	0,792	0,425	0,536	0,319
PSQ9	0,468	0,788	0,444	0,593	0,344
TS1	0,470	0,470	0,727	0,505	0,378
TS2	0,466	0,427	0,748	0,467	0,407
TS3	0,414	0,309	0,711	0,421	0,317
TS4	0,509	0,373	0,770	0,428	0,396
TS5	0,494	0,405	0,706	0,423	0,403
TS6	0,539	0,475	0,735	0,565	0,457
TS7	0,508	0,371	0,720	0,488	0,408
TS8	0,538	0,451	0,762	0,549	0,475
TS9	0,498	0,412	0,765	0,503	0,452
ITC1	0,572	0,584	0,421	0,735	0,366

Variable	UTR	PSQ	TS	ITC	RF
ITC2	0,605	0,512	0,540	0,745	0,405
ITC3	0,606	0,519	0,570	0,817	0,436
ITC4	0,524	0,494	0,507	0,770	0,409
ITC5	0,550	0,510	0,516	0,812	0,366
ITC6	0,501	0,459	0,483	0,708	0,387
ITC7	0,510	0,493	0,454	0,702	0,373
RF1	0,500	0,483	0,461	0,495	0,836
RF2	0,504	0,424	0,448	0,464	0,826
RF3	0,336	0,327	0,416	0,340	0,742
RF4	0,408	0,293	0,469	0,358	0,758
RF5	0,429	0,400	0,442	0,370	0,815

The *cross-loading* output indicates that the planned build has no low construct value, as indicated by Table 5 above. Every concept exhibits substantial or superior outcomes to other constructs, with a cross-loading value greater than 0.7. Thus, the validity test results for this study are legitimate.

Composite Reliability

Cronbach's Alpha and *Composite Reliability* are two methods for measuring *composite reliability*. The obtained value in this measurement is more than 0.70 for both Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability. The following table 6 displays the results of the composite reliability analysis.

Table 6. Composite Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
ITC	0,875	0,877	0,903	0,573
FSQ	0,919	0,921	0,932	0,580
RF	0,856	0,871	0,896	0,634
UTR	0,881	0,884	0,905	0,544
TS	0,896	0,899	0,915	0,546

Table 6 indicates that each variable has an AVE value of more than 0.50, indicating that the variable is valid and satisfies the requirements of discriminant validity. The purpose of the reliability test is to identify the instrument used to measure the construct. Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values show the reliability test value; a number greater than 0.70 is considered dependable. As a result, it can be said that the variables under test are dependable and valid.

Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT)

According to (Hair et al., 2017) a Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) value of less than 0.90 indicates an acceptable threshold level of discriminant validity. Every HTMT value is less than 0.90.

Table 7. Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT)

Variable	ITC	FSQ	RF	UTR	TS	RF x UTR	RF x FSQ	RF x TS
ITC								
FSQ	0,750							
RF	0,588	0,547						
UTR	0,826	0,729	0,625					
TS	0,738	0,612	0,636	0,745				
RF x UTR	0,133	0,207	0,253	0,129	0,232			
RF x FSQ	0,211	0,244	0,223	0,213	0,238	0,721		
RF x TS	0,219	0,233	0,283	0,236	0,265	0,766	0,676	

According to Table 7, the study's variable with the highest HTMT value is the understanding of tax regulations, scoring 0.826, whereas the variable RF x UTR has the lowest HTMT value, scoring 0.232. Furthermore, the confidence interval indicates that the resulting confidence interval (<1) was obtained by the HTMT bootstrap method. All HTMT value scores, as indicated by Table 7 HTMT, differ significantly from the value of 1.

Analysis Inner Model

R-Square (R)

Using the R-Square (R) value for endogenous latent components, one may first determine the percentage of variance explained when evaluating the PLS structural model. Changes in the R-Square value can explain the impact of some external latent variables on endogenous latent variables and whether they have a meaningful influence (Ghozali, 2021:73). This is the table 8 of R-Square (R).

Table 8. R-Square (R)

Variable	R-square	R-square adjusted
ITC	0,639	0,629

The results of the *R-Square* (R) analysis. In table 8 the *R-Square* (R) value. Individual Taxpayer Compliance (Y) is 0.639, meaning that the percentage of the amount of Individual Taxpayer Compliance (Y) that can be explained by Understanding Tax

Regulations (X1), Fiskus Service Quality (X2), Tax Sanctions (X3) and Risk Preference (Z) is 63.9%. In comparison, other variables outside the variables in this study explain the remaining 36.1%.

Hypothesis Test

The next analysis after analyzing the model is hypothesis testing. This analysis is done by comparing the T-table value with the T-statistics value. The hypothesis is declared accepted if the *T-Statistics* value > 1.65 and *P-Values* < 0.05. Table 9 shows the output table of *path coefficients* after the *bootstrapping* procedure in *smartPLS 4*.

Table 9. Path Coeffients

Variable	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Significance
FSQ -> ITC	0,285	0,288	0,053	5,395	0,000	Significance
RF -> ITC	0,053	0,057	0,047	1,134	0,257	Not Significant
UTR -> ITC	0,352	0,350	0,070	5,017	0,000	Significance
TS -> ITC	0,238	0,239	0,054	4,397	0,000	Significance
RF x UTR-> ITC	-0,086	-0,085	0,072	1,201	0,230	Not Significant
RF x FSQ -> ITC	0,037	0,040	0,060	0,614	0,539	Not Significant
RF x TS-> ITC	0,035	0,030	0,059	0,585	0,558	Not Significant

Testing the first hypothesis (H₁)

Understanding Tax Regulations on WPOP Compliance has a significant P-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, and a T-statistic of 5.017 > 1.65. Therefore, it can be said that the first hypothesis—that is, that WPOP Compliance is significantly improved by understanding tax regulations—is accepted. The findings of this study's hypothesis testing indicate that taxpayer compliance is positively impacted by tax regulatory knowledge. This is due to the fact that a high degree of taxpayer compliance in the Ciayumajakuning region is brought about by a thorough comprehension of tax legislation.

Second Hypothesis Testing (H₂)

With a significant level of P-Value of 0.000, less than 0.05, the Quality of Fiscal Services on WPOP Compliance T-statistic is 5.395 > 1.65. Therefore, it may be concluded that the second hypothesis—that is, that WPOP compliance is substantially positively influenced by the quality of fiscal services—can be accepted. As the quality of the services offered improves, so does the amount of taxpayer compliance. The study's premise was tested, and the findings show that the Ciayumajakuning region's tax authorities give their citizens excellent service, which encourages them to comply with their tax duties.

Third Hypothesis Testing (H₃)

Tax Sanctions on WPOP Compliance has a significant level of P-Value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, and a T-statistic of $4.397 > 1.65$. It follows that the third hypothesis, according to which Tax Sanctions greatly raise WPOP Compliance, is approved. Here, the goal of the tax penalties is to motivate the taxpayer to pay their taxes on time. The study's hypothesis was tested, and the findings show that tax penalties can raise taxpayer compliance in the Ciayumajakuning region.

Testing the Fourth Hypothesis (H₄)

Risk Preference on WPOP Compliance has a significant level of P-Value of 0.257, which is larger than 0.05, and a T-statistic of $1.134 < 1.65$. The fourth hypothesis, which holds that risk preference has no bearing on WPOP compliance, is thus disproved. The findings of this study's hypothesis testing indicate that WPOP in the Ciayumajakuning region does not consider the dangers involved in their choice of whether or not to file taxes. The results of this investigation have consequences for prospect theory. The onus is on taxpayers to ascertain what risks or difficulties they encounter. There is no way to categorize taxpayer compliance as high or low risk.

Fifth Hypothesis Testing (H₅)

The T-statistic is $1.201 < 1.65$ and the significant level of P-Value is 0.230, more than 0.05, for Understanding Tax Regulations with Risk Preference. Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that the fifth hypothesis is false, namely that risk preference is unable to control the relationship between taxpayer compliance and tax law knowledge. The findings of this study's hypothesis testing show that, generally speaking, taxpayers in the Ciayumajakuning area do not take the hazards involved in tax-related actions into consideration. If taxpayers are aware of the risks associated with the tax laws they are subject to, it makes little difference if they comply with their obligations or not.

Testing the Sixth Hypothesis (H₆)

With a significant P-value of 0.539 and a T-statistic of $0.614 < 1.65$, the quality of taxpayer service with risk preference is greater than 0.05. Therefore, it can be said that the sixth hypothesis is false, namely risk preference does not affect the relationship between taxpayer compliance and the quality of tax authorities' services. The premise of this study has been tested, and the findings suggest that taxpayers in the Ciayumajakuning region tend to ignore the dangers involved in tax-related activities, even when those activities are dangerous. The risks that each taxpayer faces are usually not of concern to the government or tax officials as they only deal with the appropriate procedures. It makes no difference whether taxpayers comply with their tax responsibilities or not when tax officials offer services that contain hazards.

Testing the Seventh Hypothesis (H₇)

The T-statistic is $0.585 < 1.65$ and the significant P-value is 0.558, greater than 0.05, for tax sanctions with risk preference. We therefore conclude that risk preference is either

rejected or cannot regulate the link between taxpayer compliance and tax fines. The hypothesis of the study was investigated, and the results indicate that, in general, taxpayers in the Ciayumajakuning region ignore current issues in order to avoid considering the risks associated with engaging in tax-related activities. Risk preference cannot be used to mitigate the severity of current penalties, which means it cannot make it more difficult for taxpayers to make their tax payments.

Conclusion

Based on empirical data, the results of the analysis and discussion of the problem formulation using SmartPLS 4 analysis, it can be concluded that:

1. Understanding tax regulations has a positive effect on taxpayer compliance.
2. The quality of Fiskus services has a positive effect on taxpayer compliance.
3. Tax Sanctions have a positive effect on Taxpayer Compliance.
4. Risk Preference does not affect Taxpayer Compliance.
5. Risk preferences are unable to moderate the relationship between understanding tax regulations on taxpayer compliance.
6. Risk preferences are unable to moderate the relationship between the quality of tax authorities' services on taxpayer compliance.
7. Risk preferences are unable to moderate the relationship between tax sanctions on taxpayer compliance.

Recommendations

This research is inevitably constrained by several issues that may be resolved through future research; the suggestions made in this research may help in future research. Suggestions for this research are:

1. The Government (Directorate General of Taxes) must increase socialization to disseminate information about the most recent tax regulations, including how to calculate and report taxes to be paid, applicable tax rates, and sanctions and fines imposed, in order for the general public and taxpayers to be aware of and understand the applicable tax regulations.
2. Taxpayers should increase their knowledge of pertinent tax rules in order to make it easier for them to complete their tax obligations. Achieving this requires aggressively adhering to the most recent tax legislation.
3. Future research is urged to examine additional variables like taxpayer knowledge, tax socialization, and financial condition to determine how each contributes to a higher level of taxpayer compliance. Future researchers should also increase the population

investigated to increase the number of respondents and make the research results more representative of individual taxpayers.

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